

**THE HUMANITARIAN COMPONENT IN TECHNICAL EDUCATION IS
THE BASIS FOR TRAINING STAFF FOR THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY**

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ABSTRACT. The article is devoted to the substantiation of the need to preserve and develop the humanitarian sector of education, which plays a key role in the development of students' meaningful creative imagination and the use of humanitarian knowledge to enhance personal potential and the formation of relevant aspects of engineering thinking. Completely new requirements are considered regarding the training of a specialist with a technical education in the realities of modern times, the basis of which is the humanitarian competence of the future specialist.

Key words: humanities component of engineering education, soft skills, technical education, humanities, personal development, generation Z.

Student life is an intensive process of spiritual formation and creative development for young people. It is here that the foundations for the future are laid. At the start of a student's academic career, their goals may vary: a respected profession, a stable income that allows them to start and support a family, rapid career advancement, a willingness to embark on adventures when changing locations, regions, and today, even countries and continents. However, the development of creative abilities is impossible without imagination, which is formed through the preventive formation of stable value orientations—moral, aesthetic, as well as political and legal—which requires a systematic and meaningful study of the humanities. [1], [2] The teaching of humanities disciplines, primarily cultural studies, philosophy, and political science, at a technical university involves the implementation of a competency-based approach in modern education, ensuring the unity of general cultural and professional competencies of graduates. [3] Today, professionals must be prepared to “fit in” to the broader production process, based on their ability to assess the demand for their specialty in the labor market, which in turn requires a theoretical and methodological level of knowledge and understanding of the specifics of modern ways of diversifying it. [3], [4] Broad horizons, a wealth of associations that reveal the essential content of processes unfolding in professional and social environments, the ability to diagnose the prospects or lack thereof of rationalization proposals and scientific innovations of

varying degrees of complexity based on external signs — all this requires modern specialists to constantly work on themselves spiritually.

The “qualifications” of a modern specialist should be understood as the correspondence between the requirements of the future profession and the goals of education, and the training of future specialists boils down to the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities. The trend of moving “from the concept of qualification to the concept of competence” is common throughout Europe and even worldwide, and is explained by the fact that the increasing need for knowledge and information search in modern production is not “covered” by the traditional concept of professional qualification. One of the first scholars to address the importance of humanities competence for students in technical fields was the Russian philosopher and educator Anton Makarenko. In his books, such as *Pedagogical Poem* [11], he expresses ideas about the importance of comprehensive personal development, including humanities aspects. He emphasizes that education should not be limited to narrow specialization, and that humanities knowledge is necessary for the formation of responsible and cultured specialists. The UNESCO report “Education: The Hidden Treasure” [9] states: “More and more often, entrepreneurs need not qualifications, which in their view are too often associated with the ability to perform certain material operations, but competence, which is seen as a kind of cocktail of skills inherent in each individual, combining qualifications in the strict sense of the word... social behavior, the ability to work in a group, initiative, and a love of risk.” [7] In the European contemporary Tuning project, “competence” [10] is defined very briefly as “a dynamic combination of knowledge, understanding, skills, and abilities.” [6] D.N. Ushakov's dictionary interprets “competence” as a range of issues in which a person has authority, knowledge, and experience, and “competence” as awareness and authority. [5, p. 161] The formation of “competence” presupposes the development of a student's ability to navigate diverse, including unpredictable, social and professional situations, to have an understanding of and feel responsible for the consequences of their future professional activities, based on knowledge, skills, and abilities. Currently, it is impossible to talk about the competence of a specialist with a technical education who does not possess emotional intelligence, knowledge related to humanitarian issues, communication strategies, and cultural competencies. [8, p. 80] In the course of their professional activities, specialists must be able to communicate with different people, regardless of their character traits, religious beliefs, or national characteristics. The competency-based approach is fundamentally humanitarian, as it is directly linked to the idea of comprehensive training and education of individuals not only as professionals in their field, but also as individuals, members of a team, and members of society. Consequently, the actualization of the humanitarian component of the competency-based approach involves the formation of humanitarian competence in

university students, developing their creative scientific and research activities, constructive and critical thinking, intellectual abilities, imagination, and intuition, which are necessary for successful professional activity. In today's dynamic world, it is impossible to achieve success by relying solely on the knowledge gained in higher education. It is necessary to respond quickly to changes, find solutions to problems, and, where possible, propose innovative ways to achieve results. Creativity is a quality that an engineer must have. Aspects of the social and humanitarian component of engineering education in the modern world will prove to be not only a truly important addition to the technical and natural science postulates of science, but also a fundamental basis for high-quality engineering training in all its diversity.

However, students do not pay sufficient attention to the humanities, as they consider them to be non-core subjects. As a result, there is an insufficient level of civic responsibility for professional activities, a narrow outlook among students, a lack of flexibility in thinking, poor language skills, weak command of not only foreign languages but also Russian, an inability to clearly and competently formulate their thoughts, work with scientific literature, and a poorly developed need for self-education and self-development. All of this ultimately affects the level of professional training of future specialists. Modern students are Generation Z, born between the mid-1990s and the early 2010s, who have unique opportunities thanks to the rapid development of technology and access to information, which can contribute to the active integration of the humanities into technical education and, as a result, take the humanities component of technical universities' education to a new level:

1. Access to information. It is possible to study the humanities and gain knowledge about social, environmental, and ethical issues thanks to the internet and digital resources.

2. Cross-disciplinary education. Many educational institutions are introducing programs that combine technical and humanities disciplines. One example is the STEM + Arts program, which combines science, technology, engineering, and mathematics with art and the humanities. As part of such a program, students can engage in projects where, for example, they develop innovative solutions to environmental problems using both technical skills, such as programming and modeling, and creative approaches, such as data visualization or social campaign creation. Another example is the creation of courses that focus on sustainable development in the oil and gas industry, where students study not only the technical aspects of hydrocarbon extraction and processing, but also issues of ecology, social responsibility, and economics. This allows future specialists to understand the impact of their decisions on society and nature, developing skills in systems thinking and an interdisciplinary approach.

3. Technological skills. The ability to work with modern technologies and platforms allows young professionals to create and disseminate projects aimed at sustainable development and social change, using their technical knowledge.

4. Social media. Generation Z actively uses social media to promote humanitarian ideas, exchange opinions, and draw attention to important issues, which contributes to the formation of public awareness and responsibility.

5. Activism and volunteering. Young people are eager to participate in social and environmental initiatives, which allows them to develop the leadership and collaboration skills necessary for teamwork in the oil and gas industry.

In order to encourage students to actively study the humanities and develop creative skills, modern approaches include incorporating projects, discussions, and role-playing games; using multimedia resources; inviting experts, practitioners, and representatives of various professions to discuss their experiences and the importance of humanities knowledge; holding reading clubs, art exhibitions or theatrical performances, creating conditions for student initiatives such as clubs, research groups, or volunteer projects related to the humanities, organizing field trips to museums, archives, cultural centers, or thematic exhibitions, establishing close contact between teachers and students, where teachers share their stories, experiences, and passion for the subject. The Gubkin Russian State University of Oil and Gas has successfully applied these approaches in practice. The “Navigator of Success” project was developed specifically for this purpose. The goal is to develop leadership and creative skills through a new format of interaction between students, graduate students, teachers, business experts, and representatives of government agencies. The following educational categories were identified: self-development, business, career guidance, science, patriotism, and volunteering. To successfully implement these tasks, lectures, master classes, and training sessions are organized within the university in collaboration with well-known figures in science, art, and business.

Such special projects should be implemented in all technical universities in Uzbekistan. One example is the proposed project “Humanities Readings: Dialogue between Technology and Culture,” which could include a series of seminars and master classes where students can learn the basics of the humanities through the prism of technology. Discussions on literature, art history, and cultural studies topics related to modern technological achievements could also be organized. Guest speakers, such as writers, cultural scholars, and philosophers, could share their views on the impact of technology on society and culture. In addition, students will be able to develop their own projects, exploring how humanities knowledge can be integrated into technical disciplines, which will allow them to see the importance of the humanities component in their future professional activities.

The analysis and development of these theoretical areas will ensure the training of highly qualified specialists capable of working effectively in the conditions of the fourth industrial revolution and contributing to the innovative development of society.

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